

ANALYSIS OF INTRA-YARN IMPREGNATION IN COMMINGLED YARN THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES CONSOLIDATION PROCESS

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Abstract

Laminates of braided fabrics based on glass fiber/polypropylene commingled yarns are consolidated in isothermal condition using a hot hydraulic press to investigate the influence of pressure and temperature on the impregnation quality. Micrographs are taken from the consolidated parts to investigate the micro-structure and to analyze both of the intra- and inter-bundle void contents of consolidated plates. It is found that high pressure and temperature can reduce intra-bundle porosity during consolidation, whereas high temperature may induce inter-bundle void formation. Numerical simulations based on Darcy's law are conducted as well to predict intra-bundle void content and validated by comparisons with experimental and analytical results.

1 Introduction

Fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites are widely used in many industrial sections, because of their advantages over thermoset composites, such as reduced cycle time, improved impact resistance and recycling possibility. A thermoplastic composites manufacturing cycle can be achieved in several minutes whereas advanced thermosetting composites manufacturing often takes hours for resin curing [1]. However some issues still remain, in the thermoplastic composites manufacturing process. High processing temperature which is usually greater than 200°C is required, and sometimes new processing technologies, for example fast heating and cooling systems are needed, due to the high viscosity (> 100Pa.s) of thermoplastic polymer at molten state, whereas the viscosities of thermoset resins are usually less than 1Pa.s. High viscosities require higher processing pressure or longer processing time to ensure a good impregnation of the fibrous medium at the yarn level.

Darcy's law is used to describe the resin flow in fibrous medium:

$$\vec{v} = -\frac{\mathbf{K}}{\mu} \nabla P \quad (1)$$

Or in one-dimensional (1D) form:

$$u = -\frac{K_{xx}}{\mu} \frac{\Delta P}{L} \quad (2)$$

where \vec{v} is the volume averaged fluid velocity, \mathbf{K} the permeability tensor of porous medium, μ the fluid viscosity, ∇P the local pressure gradient, u the component in x direction of \vec{v} , K_{xx} the component of \mathbf{K} in x direction, ΔP the pressure difference and L the flow distance. High viscosity μ may cause a low impregnation velocity \vec{v} , which may lead to a low degree of impregnation when a long flow distance is considered. One attractive technique to solve this problem is to reduce the flow length L [2]. Therefore some processes and materials were developed where fibers and matrix constituents are intimately mixed prior to consolidation process to provide a small flow distance for fast impregnation. Such examples are commingled (or hybrid) yarns where thermoplastic matrix fibers are mixed with reinforcement fibers,

Figure 1: Different forms of pre-mixed thermoplastic matrix composites

powder impregnation where matrix is distributed in form of powders in the spaces between reinforcing fibers, and film stacking where reinforcing fibers and film matrix layers are placed alternatively, as shown in Figure 1 [3].

A typical processing cycle of thermoplastic composites consolidation (Figure 2) consists of three major stages [2, 4]: preheating the material above the melting temperature of matrix material to allow the matrix resin to flow, applying a pre-assigned pressure for a chosen time to consolidate the commingled yarns, and cooling the material to solidification temperature (below glass transition temperature) under pressure to obtain the final product. The molten polymer matrix is impregnated into dry fiber bundles under pressure during this process. Thus, temperature, pressure and holding time are the major processing parameters that greatly affect impregnation quality. This impregnation quality, specifically residual voids in the final product, has an important influence on the mechanical properties of final parts [5, 6].

Figure 2: Commingled yarn composites consolidation process cycle

A number of studies [2, 7–13] already focused on the manufacturing and mechanical characterization of commingled yarn based composites. Many authors assumed a dry fiber yarn as a porous cylinder with a circular cross section or rectangular plate and modeled the resin flow into the fiber yarn by Darcy’s law. J. W. Seo et al. [10] proposed a one-dimensional radial resin flow model to simulate the impregnation of PEEK 150P through graphite fiber bundles. The authors showed that an increase of pressure and temperature can reduce the time for complete impregnation, and the fully impregnation can be achieved in considerably shorter time as the tow size decreased. L. Ye et al. [4] used a one-dimensional recitilinear flow model assuming a rectangular geometry yarn configuration, and presented a processing window for glass fiber/polypropylene (GF/PP) composites, which provided the compression pressure and holding time to achieve a void content lower than 2% under processing temperatures of 185 °C and 220 °C. N. Bernet et al. [2] also proposed a one-dimensional radial flow model based on Darcy’s law and compared their predictions with the experimental results of carbon fiber/polyamide12 (CA/PA12) plain weaved commingled yarn consolidation. The authors demonstrated that an increase of either holding

time or processing temperature could decrease the void content in the final part. On the other hand, an optimized applied pressure value was found, beyond which the impregnation quality decreased because of the diminution of preform permeability during consolidation. J. Bernhardsson et al. [11] presented experimental results of GF/PP warp-knitted fabric consolidation and showed the effect of processing parameters on impregnation quality as well as on the mechanical properties of consolidated laminates. M. Wysocki et al. [3] proposed a generic two-phase continuum mechanical framework, considering fibers and voids entrapped inside the yarn together as solid phase and molten matrix as fluid phase. The modeling results of fluid pressure evolution during consolidation was compared with the experimental results of GF/PP warp-knitted laminates, showing that fluid pressure was partially relaxed after a peak due to mold closing, with a residual pressure remaining in the laminate.

In all the models in the literature presented above, the shape of fiber yarn was simplified as a cylinder or a rectangular plate in the resin impregnation model for different commingled yarns and fabric structures. The real geometry of fiber yarn is quite different from this assumption, however, and generally the yarn cross-section is ellipsoidal or lenticular. Moreover, the impregnation quality was evaluated in terms of overall void content, even though there were two distinct types of voids, inter-bundle voids and intra-bundle voids.

We address these issues by numerical modeling and experimental measurements, by conducting a one-dimensional (1D) resin flow modeling assuming the circular yarn cross section and two-dimensional finite element method (2D FEM) simulation of dry fiber yarn impregnation using a realistic fiber yarn geometry. The effect of entrapped air compression inside the yarn on the impregnation quality is taken into account by two-phase simulation. To validate the model predictions, consolidation experiments of braided fabrics based on GF/PP commingled yarns are carried out under different pressure and temperature. To analyze the impregnation quality, micrographs of consolidated plates are subject to image processing for the calculation of both the intra-bundle and inter-bundle void contents.

2 Experiment investigation

2.1 Material

The material used in this work is braided fabrics of GF/PP commingled yarns. Different arrangements of commingled yarn can be considered as shown in Figure 3. Side by side arrangement commingled yarns are used in this study. The commingled yarn fabric has a fiber mass fraction of 0.7 and an areal density of 0.765 kg/m^2 , the densities of glass fibers and PP fibers are 2640 kg/m^3 and 910 kg/m^3 respectively. The yarn has an ellipsoidal cross-section, with major axis length of about 2 mm and minor axis length of about 0.6 mm. The stacking sequence used consists of seven layers of fabrics with dimensions of $150 \text{ mm} \times 150 \text{ mm}$, all arranged along the 0° yarn direction.

Figure 3: Different types of commingled yarns

2.2 Experimental procedure

Consolidation experiments are conducted under four different conditions: two different temperatures and two different pressures. The consolidation time is identical for all experiments at 5 min. The melting point of polypropylene is reported to be at 163 °C [12]. Thus the processing temperatures are chosen to be 170 °C and 210 °C. Processing conditions are listed in Table 1.

No.	T(°C)	P(MPa)	Time(min)
A	170	1.5	5
B	170	2.0	5
C	210	1.5	5
D	210	2.0	5

Table 1: Consolidation processing conditions

Consolidation experiments are carried out in a hot press (Dolouets 383, France) as shown in Figure 4. Thermocouples are used to monitor the temperature at the top and the middle of the preform. The experiment process follows the cycle in Figure 2. Firstly, the hot platens are heated to processing temperature, then a stack of commingled yarns is placed within a metallic frame between platens. The press is closed until the upper platen touches the metal frame around the commingled yarn fabric stack, to maintain the part thickness at 3 mm at lower pressure. The platen position is maintained for 5 min after both the monitored temperatures reach the processing temperature, so that the matrix resin can be considered all melted at this time. Then the pre-assigned pressure is applied by a hydraulic jack (Protomhydro) which is connected to the press. After 5 min of consolidation, the press is cooled at rate of about 0.15 °C min⁻¹ to ambient temperature and the holding pressure is maintained through the cooling process.

Figure 4: Schematic of consolidation press

2.3 Micrographic image analysis

To observe the impregnation quality and the micro-structure of consolidated parts, micrographs are taken for the transverse sections of specimens cut from the final parts, which has dimensions of 3 cm×1 cm and the same thickness as the consolidated plates. The specimens are mounted and polished with grit paper of which the finest level is 1 μm, to remove the damaged surface and to improve micrograph quality. Micrographs of different specimens are shown in Figure 5.

From the micrographs, two void types are differentiated according to their positions: intra-bundle and inter-bundle voids. To obtain the void content in the final product, image processing is conducted by converting the micrographs into white & black pictures, in which black pixels stood for voids. The pixel size of micrograph is 0.69 μm, which is much smaller than the fiber diameter of 17 μm, to ensure the accuracy of image analysis. The threshold value is set to 70, identical for all image conversions. For

Figure 5: Transverse section micrgraphs of plates consolidated under different conditions

each condition, ten micrographs are taken from the sample to form a large enough section for quantitative analysis. Then the inter-bundle and intra-bundle void contents are calculated separately.

3 Modeling and numerical simulation

In this section, two numerical models are presented, 1D radial flow model assuming the yarn cross-section as a circle and two phase flow simulation by 2D FEM employing the real shape of yarn cross-section. As the temperature is constant during the experimental consolidation process, an isothermal condition is assumed for the numerical simulations and the molten matrix is assumed to be an incompressible Newtonian fluid.

3.1 One-dimensional radial impregnation model

The 1D radial impregnation model of N. Bernet et al. [2] is employed to simulate polymer impregnation into fiber bundle. The glass fiber bundle is assumed to have a circular cross-section with a radius r_0 of 1 mm, as shown in Figure 6. It is supposed that polypropylene is already melted and forms a matrix pool around fiber bundle, then flows into fiber bundle under external pressure P_a . The resin impregnation process can be described by Darcy's law and mass conservation equation:

$$(1 - V_{f,t})u_r = -\frac{K}{\mu} \frac{\partial P}{\partial r_i} \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\partial(r_i u_r)}{\partial r_i} = 0 \quad (4)$$

where $V_{f,t}$ is the fiber volume fraction of fiber yarn, u_r the resin flow velocity in the radial direction, K the permeability of fiber yarn, μ the molten polymer viscosity, P the fluid pressure and r_i the the flow front position. From Equations (4) and (3), a relationship between flow front position and time is given [2]:

$$r_i \frac{dr_i}{dt} \ln \frac{r_i}{r_0} = -\frac{K}{(1 - V_{f,t})\mu} (P(r_i) - P_a) \quad (5)$$

using the following boundary condition:

$$P = \begin{cases} P_0 & r_i \geq r_c \\ P_0 \left(\frac{r_c}{r_i}\right)^2 & r_i < r_c \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where $P(r_i)$ is the entrapped air pressure, P_0 the initial air pressure and r_c a critical radius from which the internal pressure of the entrapped air in the fiber bundle increases following perfect gas law. $r_c = 0$ indicates that there is no air entrapped inside fiber bundle and all air is expelled by pressure during consolidation and $r_c = r_0$ means that all air inside fiber bundles is initially entrapped and compressed during the consolidation process.

Figure 6: Schematic of 1D radial flow model

In Equation (5), two constants need to be determined, namely the fiber bed permeability K and the fluid viscosity μ . The permeability is assumed to be constant during consolidation and can be described by Gebart's model [14] assuming the fiber yarn as a unidirectional composite with a hexagonal arrangement:

$$K_t = C_1 \left(\sqrt{\frac{V_{f,max}}{V_{f,t}}} - 1 \right)^{2.5} R_f^2 \quad (7)$$

$$K_l = c \frac{(1 - V_{f,t})^3}{V_{f,t}^2} \cdot R_f^2 \quad (8)$$

where K_t and K_l are the transverse and longitudinal permeabilities respectively. The model constants can be found in [14]: $C_1 = 16/9\pi\sqrt{6}$, $c = 8/57$, $V_{f,max} = \pi/2\sqrt{3}$. R_f is the glass fiber radius. In this study, the fiber volume fraction of fiber bundle $V_{f,t}$ is obtained by image analysis of fiber bundles from consolidated laminates micrographs. An averaged value of 0.67 is taken for fiber bundle permeability evaluation, which yields $K_t = 1.80 \times 10^{-13} \text{m}^2$ and $K_l = 8.12 \times 10^{-13} \text{m}^2$. The transverse permeability is taken for the 1D radial impregnation case as $K = K_t$.

As the flow velocity during consolidation is quite low, resin impregnation process can be considered as a creeping flow with a low shear rate [15]. Therefore, the molten PP matrix can be assumed to be a Newtonian fluid and its viscosity is only a function of temperature, which can be described by an Arrhenius equation:

$$\mu = \mu_0 e^{\frac{\Delta E}{T}} \quad (9)$$

where μ_0 is the polymer viscosity at a reference temperature and ΔE the activation energy. The values for polypropylene viscosity are taken from reference [15]: $\mu_0 = 0.6075 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$ and $\Delta E = 3315 \text{ K}$.

The intra-bundle void content can be defined as the ratio of unfilled section area to the total fabric section area.

$$\text{Void content} = \frac{A_{\text{unfilled}}}{A_{\text{total}}} = \frac{A_{\text{unfilled}}}{A_{\text{yarn}}/V_{f,yarn}} = \frac{r_i^2}{r_0^2} \cdot (1 - V_{f,t}) \cdot V_{f,yarn} \quad (10)$$

Where $V_{f,yarn}$ is the yarn volume fraction over the commingled fabric.

3.2 Two-dimensional FEM simulation

In 1D radial flow model, the fiber bundle is assumed to have a circular section, whereas in real cases, the geometrical configuration of fiber bundle is closer to an ellipse. Furthermore, the longitudinal and transverse permeabilities K_l, K_t are not identical within the same yarn. More crucial is the determination of the yarn cross-section radius (r_0) and of the critical radius for air compression onset r_c . As a matter of fact, the accuracy of the modeling results highly depend on these two parameters that should be decided from trials-and-errors to better fit the experimental data, because they are not intrinsic material parameters. Thus a 2D FEM model based on Darcy's law is established to consider the real fiber yarn geometry and the air flow effect during consolidation process.

Above all, a representative elementary volume (REV) is taken for the simulation domain based on a consolidated laminate micrograph. The micrograph and corresponding geometry of 2D FEM mesh are presented in Figure 7. The fiber bundles are assumed to have elliptical sections, while polymer matrix is assumed to be at molten state and placed around the fiber bundles.

Figure 7: Yarn section geometry and the corresponding FEM mesh

In this study, the resin is assumed at molten state and fully fill the space between dry fiber yarns. Only resin impregnation is considered, whereas the fiber bed deformation is neglected. Two different cases, with and without air flow, are considered in this model. The impregnation simulation with air flow is conducted by the tow-phase flow model, and the one without air flow is conducted by the single phase flow model. In single phase model, only the polymer matrix flow is considered, for the impregnated zone:

$$\nabla \cdot \left(\frac{K}{\mu_m} \nabla P \right) = 0 \quad (11)$$

where μ_m polymer is the polymer viscosity. For the two phase model, the air flow is taken into account, for the dry fiber zone using the following governing equation while the same governing equation (Equation (11)) is used for the impregnated zone [16].

$$\frac{1 - V_f}{p_a} \frac{\partial P_a}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{K}{\mu_a} \nabla P_a \right) \quad (12)$$

where P_a is the air pressure, and μ_a the air viscosity.

The fiber bundle permeability is calculated according to Gebart's model (Equation (7) and (8)). The dependency of polymer viscosity on temperature is given by Equation (9). The external pressure is

applied directly to the fluid in the open space between fiber tows as the boundary conditions. It is assumed that there is enough polymer matrix for the impregnation and two zero pressure points are assigned at the middle of boundary edges for transverse fiber bundle, allowing the air to flow out of the bundle.

4 Results and discussion

The experimental results for inter and intra-bundle void contents are shown in Table 2. It can be seen from the results that as pressure and temperature increase, intra-bundle void content decreases, whereas this is not necessarily true for inter-bundle content which is much higher for high temperature condition. The total void content can be increased for high temperature condition due to high inter-bundle void content.

	A	B	C	D
Intra-bundle	1.02%	0.79%	0.52%	0.41%
Inter-bundle	0.17%	0.29%	1.77%	1.55%
Total	1.19%	1.08%	2.29%	1.96%

Table 2: Image analysis results for porosities

The numerical prediction by 1D radial flow model is shown in Figure 8. The results by 2D FEM simulation is presented in Figure 9, where the evolution of flow front position along time is represented for both single phase and two phase flow models. The void content as a function of impregnation time is plotted as well in Figure 10 for tow-phase flow case. Also, a comparison of numerical and experimental results is presented in Figure 11.

Figure 8: Porosity evolution with time under different processing condition with different r_c value

Figure 9: Two-phases and single-phase modeling results by 2D FEM simulation

Figure 10: Void content evolution of 2D FEM simulation

For the 1D model, from the results in Figure 8 and 11, it can be seen that both high temperature and pressure can improve the impregnation quality. High temperature can reduce the polymer viscosity and high pressure induces a high resin velocity. In $r_c = 0$ case, all conditions except condition A

Figure 11: Intra-bundle void content comparison of experimental and numerical results

(170 °C, 1.5 MPa) where pressure and temperature are low can achieve full impregnation within five minutes of consolidation. However this is not true if air is entrapped inside fiber bundles. Entrapped air is compressed during consolidation by external pressure and the pressure inside air voids increases as compression continues. When air pressure is equal to external pressure, air bubbles can not be compressed any more and these bubbles form voids after cooling. This is why both in $r_c = 0.5r_0$ and $r_c = r_0$ cases, there is non-zero a residual void content for all conditions.

From the results of 2D FEM simulation, it can be seen that for single phase flow, full impregnation is achieved within five minutes for all conditions, which agrees with the results obtained from the 1D radial flow model. This implies that in an ideal condition where there is no air entrapment during consolidation (for example, in a vacuum assisted process), the fiber bundle can be fully impregnated easily. On the other hand, for two phase flow model, none of the conditions leads to full impregnation. The unfilled areas are present in the center of the yarn for both longitudinal and transverse yarns. In the transverse yarn, the voids are more abundant at the sides of yarn which could be caused by air venting effect, making the air voids migrate towards the free boundaries during the consolidation process.

From the comparison between Figures 8 and 10, it can be concluded that the 2D FEM result of void content evolution is similar to the results of 1D radial flow model. Higher temperature and higher pressure can accelerate the impregnation velocity significantly. But the void contents from 2D simulation are much higher than the experiment results, the reason is that the cooling process takes few hours as the cooling rate is very slow, and during this time the pressure is maintained, which induces extra impregnation time for consolidation, this also explains why a relative good impregnation quality is obtained for all conditions.

The experimental result shows that inter-bundle void contents are much higher at high temperature condition. The most reasonable explanation is the polymer shrinkage and fiber bed elastic release during cooling which could cause voids and their growth in the matrix rich region. The polymer matrix could have a high crystallization degree with a low cooling rate, which leads to a high shrinkage degree. Another important point is the pressure drop during cooling process. As temperature decreases, polymer begins to crystallize and shrink. The press platen can not continue to compress the material as its position is maintained by the metal blocks, which induces the holding pressure drop on the laminates during cooling process. This pressure drop was observed during experiments and also found both in numerical simulations and experiments in [3]. Therefore higher inter-bundle void contents were obtained at high

temperature conditions as a higher initial cooling temperature leads to a higher shrinkage degree.

A supplement plate was consolidated under 210 °C and 2 MPa to show the influence of cooling rate on the residual void content. The plate was translated into a cold press after 5 minutes of consolidation to cool down with pressure maintained, and it was cooled to room temperature in few minutes. The micrograph analysis gives an intra-bundle void of 2.43% and an inter-bundle void of 0.35%, this result have a good agreement with the total void content of $2.97\% \pm 0.12\%$ given by density measurement and calcination test. Thus it can be conducted that the cooling rate is another parameter needed to be control during consolidation process.

5 Conclusion

Consolidation experiments were conducted under different processing parameters to study the influence of temperature and pressure conditions on impregnation quality. Both intra-bundle and inter-bundle voids were observed in micrographs and the void contents were separately evaluated based on image analysis. It was shown that high temperature and high pressure could decrease intra-bundle void content, resulting in final products with a satisfying void content level. On the other hand, increasing processing temperature, might generate inter-bundle voids. Also the low cooling rate and the polymer shrinkage during cooling process could explain the high inter-bundle void level under high temperature processing condition.

Simulations with different numerical models were conducted as well to predict the consolidation quality. The fiber bundle impregnation results of 1D radial flow model and 2D FEM simulation showed that a fast fully impregnation could be achieved if air compression or air flow was not taken into account. If air compression effect was considered, voids could not be totally eliminated which correspond to the experimental results. Compared with 1D model, the 2D FEM simulation can take into account the geometrical configuration of fiber bundle and as well the permeability variation of yarn along different directions. This offers an opportunity to simulate consolidation process with more complex and realistic preform geometry.

The inter-bundle void formation mechanism and the influence of processing parameters on it still need to be investigated in the further study and the polymer shrinkage during cooling process could draw our attention.

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